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Abstract

This paper provides an overview of the link between food insecurity and violent conflict, addressing both traditional and emerging threats to security and political stability. It discusses the effects of food insecurity on several types of conflict and the political, social, and demographic factors that may exacerbate these effects. It then discusses the interventions that can break the link between food security and conflict, focusing on mechanisms that can shield consumers and producers from food price shocks. Food insecurity – especially when caused by a rise in food prices – is a threat and impact multiplier for violent conflict. It might not be a direct cause and rarely the only cause, but combined with other factors, for example in the political or economic spheres, it could be the factor that determines whether and when violent conflicts will erupt. Changes in food security, rather than levels of food insecurity, are probably the most influential. Food insecurity is neither a necessary nor a sufficient condition for violent conflict. Food price stabilization measures and safety nets are critical instruments to prevent violent conflict. Food assistance can contribute to peacebuilding, restore trust in governments and rebuild social capital. Finally, it discusses ways in which the international community can assist in breaking this link and build peace.

Keywords; *insecurity, food, violence, security and war.*

I. Introduction

Rising food prices contribute to food insecurity, which is a clear and serious threat to human security. Interest in food security as a catalyst for political instability and conflict has grown rapidly since 2007–2008 when food protests and riots broke out in 48 countries as a result of record world prices. In February 2011, the food price index of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) reached a new historic peak, and the rise in food prices contributed to the wave of protests across North Africa and the Middle East that toppled Tunisian President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali and Egyptian President Hosni Mubarak.

Among major development organizations, the unchallenged consensus is that war and conflict are development issues: conflict ravages local economies, often leading to forced migration, refugee populations, disease, a collapse of social trust, and acute food insecurity. But is food insecurity itself a cause of conflict? Based on a review of recent research, the answer is a highly qualified yes. Food insecurity, especially when caused by higher food prices, heightens the risk of democratic breakdown, civil conflict, protest, rioting, and communal conflict. The evidence linking food insecurity to interstate conflict is less strong, though there is some historical evidence linking declining agricultural yields to periods of regional conflict in Europe and Asia.

These links are highly context-specific: they are contingent on existing political institutions, levels of economic development, social safety nets and demographic pressures. Food insecurity is neither a necessary nor sufficient condition for acute political violence and conflict. Generally, the risk of violent conflict is higher where political regimes intermingle democratic and authoritarian institutions or when a youth bulge, low levels of development, deteriorating economic conditions, or high inequalities among groups are present. Fragile states (which have a high share of food imports), and the households within them (who must spend a large share of their income on food), are particularly vulnerable to higher food prices. Moreover, this vulnerability has increased over time. On the other hand, violent conflicts have also contributed to higher food prices and food insecurity, contributing to a vicious cycle.

While the situation seems bleak, the contingent nature of food insecurity's effect on conflict suggests that governments, international organizations (IO's), and non-governmental organizations (NGO's) can take positive steps to reduce food insecurity and break the relationship between food insecurity and conflict. Governments can act to shield their citizens from higher prices and volatility in world markets by initiating measures to stabilize food prices and by establishing social protection systems that mitigate the impact of high food prices on vulnerable groups. Unfortunately, the capacity of fragile states to do that is limited. The World Food Programme and NGO's can assist in times of acute crisis to provide relief. Finally, governments, IOs and NGOs can work to make food security a part of the post-conflict peacebuilding and reconstruction process. The challenges are great, but the potential social, economic, and political costs of inaction are even greater.

Food Insecurity as a Cause of Violence

The traditional security paradigm focuses on military threats to sovereign states. The absence of war, however, does not equal peace and stability. Between 1990 and 2009, Kenya experienced neither interstate nor intrastate war, yet political and social violence, including election-related rioting, communal conflict and cattle raiding caused over 4,700 deaths.¹ Civil conflict and interstate war are merely the most obvious manifestations of political violence; other types of conflict may pose similarly grave threats to human security.

The Roman poet Juvenal recognized in 100 CE that the provision of "bread and circuses" was an effective mechanism for garnering public support and preventing the populace from expressing discontent. Contemporary observers note that it is not only the level of insecurity that matters but also how this insecurity is distributed. Relative deprivation, rather than absolute deprivation, generate grievances that motivate violent behaviour. Thus, many of the studies linking economic grievances to conflict look at

¹ Salehyan, I., Hendrix, C.S., Case, C., Linebarger, C., Stull, E. & Williams, J. 2011. The Social Conflict in Africa Database: New Data and Applications. Working Paper, University of North Texas.

both the average level of food insecurity and at whether that food insecurity is widely experienced or concentrated in certain groups.²

Most of the types of political violence addressed here are more prevalent in societies with higher levels of chronic food insecurity. There is a correlation between food insecurity and political conflict in part because both are symptoms of low development.³ Nevertheless, a growing body of research makes both direct links and indirect links – as proxied by environmental scarcity or access to water resources – between food scarcity and various types of conflict.

Theories tend to rest either on the perspective of motivation, emphasizing the effect of food insecurity on economic and social grievances; or on the perspective of the opportunity cost, emphasizing the perceived costs and benefits of participating in violence relative to other means of securing income or food.⁴ These arguments are most valid concerning participation in civil war and rebellion, where participation is better explained by a mixture of grievances – which provide motivation – and selective incentives – protection from violence and opportunities to engage in predation or to receive food, clothing, shelter and other material benefits – rather than grievances alone.⁵ A study of demobilized combatants in Sierra Leone found that poverty, lack of educational access and material rewards were associated with participation in the civil war.⁶ Interestingly, in Liberia, women were more likely than men to fight for material benefits. Thus, grievances are important, but so are motivations related to that individual's economic and opportunistic considerations.

Civil Conflict

Civil conflict is the prevalent type of armed conflict in the world today. It is almost exclusively a phenomenon of countries with low levels of economic development and high levels of food insecurity. Sixty-five per cent of the world's food-insecure people live in seven countries: India, China, the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Bangladesh, Indonesia, Pakistan and Ethiopia,⁷ of which all but China have experienced

² Reenock, C., Bernhard, M. & Sobek, D. 2007. Regressive Socioeconomic Distribution and Democratic Survival. *International Studies Quarterly*, 51(3): 677–699.

³ Collier, P., Elliot, L., Hegre, H., Hoeffler, A., Sambanis, N. & Reynal-Querol, M. 2003. *Breaking the Conflict Trap: Civil War and Development Policy*. Oxford, Oxford University Press.

⁴ Gurr, T.R. 1970. *Why Men Rebel*. Princeton, Princeton University Press.

⁵ Berman, E. 2009. *Radical, Religious, and Violent: The New Economics of Terrorism*. Cambridge, MIT Press.

⁶ Humphreys, M.A. & Weinstein, J.M. 2008. Who Fights? The Determinants of Participation in Civil War. *American Journal of Political Science*, 52(2): 436–455.

⁷ FAO. 2010. FAOSTAT Database. Rome, FAO. Accessed April 28, 2021. <http://faostat.fao.org/>

civil conflict in the past decade, with DRC, Ethiopia, India and Pakistan currently embroiled in civil conflicts.

Pinstrup-Andersen and Shimokawa,⁸ find that poor health and nutrition are associated with a greater probability of civil conflict, though their findings are based on small sample sizes. Countries with lower per capita caloric intake are more prone to experience civil conflict, even accounting for their levels of economic development.⁹ This relationship is stronger in those states where primary commodities make up a large proportion of their export profile. Some of the countries most plagued by conflict in the past 20 years are commodity-rich countries characterized by widespread hunger, such as Angola, DRC, Papua New Guinea and Sierra Leone. The mixture of hunger – which creates grievances – and the availability of valuable commodities – which can provide opportunities for rebel funding – is a volatile combination.

World commodity prices can trigger conflict, as higher prices, especially for food, increase affected groups' willingness to fight. Timothy Besley and Torsten Persson¹⁰ find that as a country's import prices increase, thereby eroding real incomes, the risk of conflict increases. Oeindrila Dube and Juan F. Vargas arrive at similar conclusions when looking at Colombia, where higher export prices for coffee (which is labour intensive and a source of rural income) reduced violence in coffee-producing areas while higher export prices for oil (which is capital intensive and a source of income for rebels and paramilitary groups) increased violence in regions with oil reserves and pipelines.

Other research links transitory weather shocks to civil conflict. In these studies, weather shocks – like drought and excess rainfall – are thought to fuel conflict by causing crops to fail and reducing agricultural employment opportunities, thus increasing food insecurity both in terms of food availability and food access (ability to pay). The people most likely to participate in armed conflict – young men from rural areas with limited education and economic prospects – are likely to seek work in the agricultural sector. As that work dries up, fighting looks more attractive. However, the empirical link between transitory weather shocks and civil conflict is still ambiguous. Some studies find that civil conflict is more likely to begin following years of negative growth in rainfall,¹¹ suggesting that drought and decreased agricultural productivity expand the pool of potential combatants and give rise to more broadly held grievances. However, approaches that look at levels of rainfall, rather than growth in rainfall from year to year, find tenuous, or positive relationships, between rainfall abundance and the

⁸ Pinstrup-Andersen, P. & Shimokawa, S. 2008. Do Poverty and Poor Health and Nutrition Increase the Risk of Armed Conflict Onset? *Food Policy*, 33(6): 513–520.

⁹ Sobek, D. & Boehmer, C. 2009. If They Only Had Cake: The Effect of Food Supply on Civil War Onset, 1960–1999. Unpublished manuscript.

¹⁰ Timmer, C.P. 2010. Reflections on food crises past. *Food Policy*, 35: 1–11.

¹¹ Hendrix, C.S. & Glaser, S.M. 2007. Trends and Triggers: Climate, Climate Change, and Civil Conflict in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Political Geography*, 26(6): 695–715.

onset of conflict.¹² Some case-based research, however, links drought to conflict – though mediated by the government’s response to the crisis. For example, during the Tuareg rebellion in northern Mali, drought – aggravated by the government’s embezzlement of drought relief supplies and food aid – was a significant source of grievance that motivated young men and women to take up arms.¹³

Recently, warmer temperatures have been linked to an increase in civil conflict, though this finding has been challenged.¹⁴ Civil war is also more likely in the aftermath of quick-onset natural disasters, such as earthquakes, major volcanic eruptions, floods, and cyclonic storms.¹⁵ The relationship between disaster and conflict is strongest in countries with high levels of inequality and slow economic growth; food insecurity and resource scarcity are among the more plausible explanations for this correlation.

Interstate War

The links between food insecurity and interstate war are less direct. While countries often go to war over territory, previous research has not focused directly on access to food or productive agricultural land as a major driver of conflict.¹⁶ (Hensel, 2000). However, wars have been waged to reduce demographic pressures arising from the scarcity of arable land, the clearest examples being the move to acquire Lebensraum (“living space”) that motivated Nazi Germany’s aggression toward Poland and Eastern Europe,¹⁷ and Japan’s invasion of China and Indochina.¹⁸ Water, for drinking and agriculture, is also a cause of conflict.¹⁹ Countries that share river basins are more likely

¹² Burke, M.B., Miguel, E., Satyanath, S., Dykema, J.A. & Lobell, D.B. 2009. Warming Increases the Risk of Civil War in Africa. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(49): 20670–20674.

¹³ Berdal, M.R. & Malone, D.M. 2000. *Greed and Grievance: Economic Agendas in Civil Wars*. Boulder, Lynne Rienner Publishers.

¹⁴ Buhaug, H. 2010. Climate not to blame for African civil wars. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(38): 16477–16482.

¹⁵ Nel, P. & Righarts, M. 2008. Natural Disasters and the Risk of Violent Civil Conflict. *International Studies Quarterly*, 52(1): 159–185.

¹⁶ Hensel, P.R. 2000. Territory: Theory and Evidence on Geography and Conflict. In *What Do We Know About War?* ed. J.A. Vasquez. New York, Rowman and Littlefield, pp. 57–84.

¹⁷ Hensel, P.R. 2000. Territory: Theory and Evidence on Geography and Conflict. In *What Do We Know About War?* ed. J.A. Vasquez. New York, Rowman and Littlefield, pp. 57–84.

¹⁸ Natsios, A.S. & Doley, K.W. 2009. The Coming Food Coups. *The Washington Quarterly*, 32(1): 7–25.

¹⁹ Klare, M.T. 2002. *Resource Wars: The New Landscape of Global Conflict*. New York, Owl Books.

to go to war than are other countries that border one another.²⁰ This relationship is strongest in countries with low levels of economic development. Institutions that manage conflicts over water and monitor and enforce agreements can significantly reduce the risk of war.

Democratic and Authoritarian Breakdowns

Democratic breakdowns occur when leaders are deposed and replaced by officials who come to power without regard for elections, legal rules, and institutions. Not all breakdowns are violent – "bloodless" coups account for 67 per cent of all coups and coup attempts – but many have been very bloody, and the autocratic regimes and instability that follow democratic breakdowns are more likely to lead to the abuse of human rights, in some cases leading to mass state killing.²¹

Protest and Rioting

International market prices are not the only source of food-related protests. The lifting of government subsidies can lead to rioting as well. Until recently, the biggest demonstrations in modern Egyptian history were the three-day "bread riots" in 1977 that killed over 800 people, which were a response to the Egyptian government's removal of state subsidies for basic foodstuffs, as mandated by the International Monetary Fund (IMF).²² "IMF riots" can be traced to popular grievances over withdrawn food and energy subsidies.²³ However, the relationship between "IMF riots" and food insecurity is more complicated. Generalized food and energy subsidies are regressive, meaning that wealthy and middle-class households generally capture more of the benefits. As such, it may be real income erosion, rather than acute food insecurity, that is driving participation in the protest.

Communal Violence

Competition over scarce resources, particularly land and water, often causes or exacerbates communal conflict.²⁴ Communal conflict involves groups with permanent or semi-permanent armed militias but does not involve the government. However, it can

²⁰Gleditsch, N.P., Furlong, K., Hegre, H., Lacina, B. & Owen, T. 2006. Conflicts over Shared Rivers: Resource Scarcity or Fuzzy Boundaries? *Political Geography*, 25(4): 361–382.

²¹Poe, S.C. & Tate, C.N. 1994. Repression of Human Rights to Personal Integrity in the 1980s: A Global Analysis. *The American Political Science Review*, 88(4): 853–872.

²²Agence France Presse. 2007. 30 Years After Bread Riots, Egypt Reform Moves Forward. January 21. Posted at: <http://www.dailystaregypt.com/article.aspx?ArticleID=5112>.

²³Walton, J. & Seddon, D. 1994. *Free Markets and Food Riots: The Politics of Global Adjustment*. New York, Wiley-Blackwell. See also- Abouharb, M.R. & Cingranelli, D.L. 2007. *Human Rights and Structural Adjustment: The Impact of the IMF and the World Bank*. New York, Cambridge University Press.

²⁴Ban, K. 2007. A Climate Culprit in Darfur. *Washington Post*, 16 June.

escalate to include government forces, as in the massacres in Darfur, Rwanda, Nigeria and Burundi. These conflicts have the potential to escalate to civil war when the government is perceived to be supporting, tacitly or otherwise, one communal group at the expense of the other.²⁵ While the conflict in Darfur began as a communal conflict over land and water, its impact escalated to devastating proportions following the government's support for Janjaweed militias in their fight against the Sudan People's Liberation Army/Movement and Justice and Equality Movement rebels.

Communal conflicts are common in the Sahel, the zone of transition between the Sahara Desert and the savanna, particularly in years of extremely high and low rainfall. Recurrent, long-lasting droughts in the Sahel have undermined cooperative relationships between migratory herders and sedentary farmers, leading to food insecurity and increased competition for water and land between farmers and herders, but also within herding and farming groups. As a pastoralist in Sudan noted: "When there is food, there is no cattle raiding."²⁶ Once violence begins, conflict escalates and persists because of security dilemmas (fear of future attacks leads to preemptive attacks) and lack of alternative dispute mechanisms between groups and effective policing within groups.

These conflicts have been particularly lethal in Kenya, Nigeria, the Sudan and Uganda. Repeated clashes between Fulani herders and farmers in Nigeria's Plateau and the Benue States killed 843 people in 2020. Similar clashes between Rizeigat Abbala and Terjam herders in Sudan killed 382 in 2007. Cattle raiding in the Karamoja Cluster, a cross-border region of Ethiopian, Kenyan and Ugandan territory, resulted in more than 600 deaths and the loss of 40,000 heads of livestock in 2004 alone.²⁷ These conflicts tend to occur in politically marginalized territories far from the capital.²⁸

Finally, urbanization has cross-cutting impacts on political violence that interact with food insecurity in complex ways. When rural populations move to the city, they increase the ratio of food consumers to producers and it is more difficult for them to turn to subsistence farming as a coping mechanism for dealing with higher food prices.

²⁵ Iannaccone, L.R. & Berman, E. 2006. Religious Extremism: The Good, the Bad, and the Deadly. *Public Choice*, 128(1-2): 109-129.

²⁶ Schomerus, M. & Allen, T. 2010. *Southern Sudan at Odds with Itself: Dynamics of Conflict and Predicaments of Peace*. London, London School of Economics.

²⁷ Maier, R. 2010. Early recovery in post-conflict countries: a conceptual study. Conflict Research Unit, the Netherlands Institute of International Relations, Clingendael. Also- Fearon, J.D. & Laitin, D.D. 2003. Ethnicity, Insurgency, and Civil War. *American Political Science Review*, 97(1):75-90.

²⁸ Raleigh, C. 2010. Political Marginalization, Climate Change, and Conflict in the African Sahel States. *International Studies Review*, 12(1): 69-86.

However, urban populations are more easily served by food distribution networks and safety nets and tend to receive more attention from political actors because of their capacity for collective protest.²⁹

Political Institutions The type of political regime – whether a country is democratic, autocratic, or intermingles democratic and autocratic institutions – has complex effects on political violence. Highly repressive authoritarian regimes may create incentives for clandestine action such as insurgency or revolution, but these regimes are generally well-positioned to deter and repress public protest.³⁰ Peaceful protest should be more common where citizens are either legally allowed to engage in demonstrations, as in democracies, or where authoritarian governments choose to tolerate such acts of dissent, as in “semi-authoritarian” or hybrid regimes. Democratic institutions give politicians incentives to address societal concerns, which may diminish the grievances that motivate protest and rebellion.

Focus on the Fragile States

Higher international prices do not necessarily mean higher domestic prices. Whether they do depend on structural factors such as how dependent the country is on food imports, transportation costs and market competitiveness; and on policy measures including trade barriers, taxes and subsidies, and government interventions.³¹

Households in fragile states are particularly vulnerable to higher food prices. Fragile and conflict-affected states often suffer from a lack of infrastructure, in particular passable roads, markets with few buying or selling offers and a lack of entrepreneurs, leading to less competitive markets and higher transportation costs. They also import large share of their food and have fewer means to stabilize food prices and mitigate the impact of higher food prices on the population.

The dependency of fragile states on imports has accelerated over time, especially relative to other developing countries. Imported food as a share of total food consumption is higher in fragile states than in other developing countries, increasing the vulnerability of fragile states to international price movements.

Violent Conflict as a Source of Higher Prices

²⁹ Bates, R.H. 2011. Food Price Shocks and Political Instability. USAID CMM Discussion Paper No. 3. Washington DC.

³⁰ Goodwin, J. 2001. No Other Way Out: States and Revolutionary Movements, 1945–1991. New York, Cambridge University Press.

³¹ WFP. 2009b. Full Report of the Evaluation of the Liberia PRRO 10454.0 (July 2007–June 2000). Office of Evaluation.

Violent conflict itself has historically been an important factor behind high food prices and severe food insecurity. Following World War II, countries particularly affected include Angola (the early 1980s), Cambodia (1979–1980), Ethiopia (1984–1985), Mozambique (1980s), Nigeria (1967–1969), Somalia (1992) and Sudan (1987–1991).³²

Conflict typically brings increased military spending and the domestic use of military force, both of which have contributed to food security and child hunger.³³ Conflict often affects the ability to produce, trade and access food.³⁴ Violent conflict causes death, disease and displacement, destroys physical and social capital, damages the environment, decreases school attendance and discourages investment. It crowds out a normal economic activity such as food production, destroys infrastructure and cuts off access to food supplies, with blocking of food access often used as a tool of political terror.³⁵

Refugees and internally displaced persons fleeing violence often experience the most acute insecurity. The civil war in Southern Sudan left an estimated 2.6 million people in need of emergency food aid by 2000; since the conflict in Darfur broke out in 2003, roughly 2 million people have been displaced. World Food Programme has had to provide monthly food rations to nearly all of those people. More recently, Somali pirates have targeted food-carrying vessels, driving up prices of staples like wheat and rice by up to 22 per cent.³⁶

Political instability and conflict push food prices higher in both local and international markets. The 2011 protests across North Africa and the Middle East were in part a response to higher food and fuel prices, but the instability they have sown has in turn roiled commodity markets, including markets for oil, a key agricultural input.

Though food insecurity contributes to violent conflict and political instability, food insecurity is neither a necessary nor sufficient condition for it. Governments, IOs and NGOs can help reduce food insecurity and break the food insecurity–conflict link.

³² Drèze, J. & Sen, A.K. 1989. *Hunger and Public Action*. Oxford, Clarendon Press. ; Ó Gráda, Cormac. 2009. *Famine: A Short History*. Princeton, Princeton University Press.

³³ Scanlan, S.J. & Jenkins, J.C. 2001. *Military Power and Food Security: A Cross-National Analysis of Less-Developed Countries, 1970–1990*. *International Studies Quarterly*, 45(1): 159–187.

³⁴ United Nations. 1993. *World Economic Survey, 1993*. New York, United Nations.

³⁵ Alderman, H. & Hoddinott, J. 2007. *Growth promoting social safety nets*. IFPRI Policy Brief. Washington DC, IFPRI. Posted at: www.ifpri.org/2020Chinaconference/pdf/beijingbri_ef_alderman.pdf.

³⁶ IRIN. 2010. *Somalia: Pirates Target Food, Pushing Up Prices*. April 12. http://www.alertnet.org/thenews/newsdesk/IRIN/9_95f6300f0835982ace2b91f47b3e460.htm.

The fragile States and Political Capacity

Fragile states have weak capacities to design, implement and monitor policies and programmes. They have less capacity to stabilize food prices – in part because they cannot analyse markets – and to mitigate the impact of volatile and high food prices, which would require the capacity to design, target, implement and monitor safety nets. Many fragile states don't have the various capacities required by cash-based programmes, nor the weather stations and analytical and implementation capacity required for weather-based index insurance. Food reserves can be looted when security is weak, and fiscal capacity is often severely reduced.

Many fragile countries have experienced recurrent fiscal crises since the early 1980s that have severely curtailed their ability to intervene in domestic markets and ensure food security. Moreover, chronic problems of macroeconomic instability, high external debts and policy conditionality make it prohibitively costly for many countries to borrow in tough times and ensure domestic consumption and food security by engaging in counter-cyclical social spending.³⁷

The contributions in this paper all reveal a complex interplay among local, regional and international forces. In general terms, they confirm our contention “that state authority has leaked away, upwards, sideways, and downwards” However, while in the OECD world this “diffusion of authority away from the state” can still be associated with the substitution of military strife by economic competition, this book demonstrates that this move towards “perpetual peace” does not reflect the social reality in large parts of the world. On the contrary, the studies presented here show that the “*commercialization of international relations*” has also been accompanied by the resurrection of methods of primitive accumulation. Current war economies present combinations of primitive accumulation with more sophisticated modes of economic reproduction. The political economy of intra-state wars comprises looting, pillaging and robbery at gunpoint, as well as the establishment of protection rackets that temporarily assume state-like forms of extraction by levying tolls and taxes on the territories under their control. On the one hand, these war economies derive their revenues from a variety of local resources, for instance by monopolizing trade and production, exploiting natural resources or enforcing labour and slavery. On the other hand, war economies interrelate not only with illegal global markets, such as those involved in the drugs and arms trade, but also very closely with formal international markets, and their financial means come to a substantial degree from humanitarian aid, foreign military assistance and political rents.

II. Conclusion

³⁷Wibbels, E. 2006. Dependency Revisited: International Markets, Business Cycles and Social Spending in the Developing World. *International Organization*, 60(2): 433–469.

Food insecurity is both a cause and a consequence of violence, contributing to a vicious cycle or “conflict trap”. Food security is critical for political stability. Food insecurity is linked to increased risk of democratic failure, protests and rioting, communal violence and civil conflict. Violent conflicts, in turn, create food insecurity, malnutrition and – in some instances – famine. Thus food insecurity can perpetuate conflict, although its effects depend on the context, with the strongest links evident in states that already have fragile markets and weak political institutions.

Food price stabilization measures are important tools to prevent food prices from rising and causing unrest. Safety nets are critical instruments that can mitigate the effect of short-term spikes in food prices on food insecurity, helping to prevent violent conflict and contribute to long-term development. Because young men as a group are most in need of livelihoods and also most likely to participate in political violence, income instability among them must be addressed. Safety nets have the added advantage of mitigating horizontal inequalities, which are one cause of conflict.

International food assistance plays an important role both during conflicts and in the post-conflict recovery period. International organizations such as WFP and NGOs are particularly important in these situations because of reduced government capacity to provide basic services in states experiencing conflict and because of the perceived impartiality of aid workers.

After decades of consistent gains in eradicating hunger, food insecurity is once again on the rise. The effects of food insecurity on human security are dire, as are the consequences for political stability and conflict. Though the challenge is great, the international community – and World Food Programme in particular – can play a positive role in addressing hunger and breaking the link between food insecurity and conflict. Finally, we have to ask whether this decisive change in the relationship between war-making and state-making in a globalizing world is adequately captured by terms such as *new wars* or *intra-state wars*. It is certainly not surprising that the blurring of political authority and economic appropriation finds its equivalent in the blurring of the distinctions between war, organized crime and large-scale violations of human rights. This is because our concepts of legitimate political authority, formal economic exchange, and forms of violence are essentially structured by the social institution of the modern state. More specifically, both the blurred pictures of political economy and of forms of violence are two sides of the defective state. But do these findings allow us to speak of “new” or “postmodern” wars?

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